

Investigation of the effect of different coastal dam types on wave overtopping

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ABSTRACT

Climate change has significantly exacerbated coastal erosion. Thus, implementing coastal dams is crucial in reducing wave overtopping and mitigating the effects of climate change. The three commonly used coastal dam structures are vertical seawalls, curved seawalls, and riprap dams. Along with these, we designed three more dam models (triangular, zigzag, and inverted triangle) for this investigation, possessing characteristics similar to those as mentioned earlier commonly used dams. Through this research, we used such physical models to understand how different dam designs affect seawater overtopping by creating in-phase waves or redirecting wave impact and diffusing wave energy. We used compressed foam models to simulate wave impacts in a wave tank across 6 different wave frequencies to analyse which dam designs are most suitable in preventing the overtopping of seawater at coastal areas through the smallest maximum vertical displacements of water, concluding that the inverted dam is the most effective in reducing overtopping due to the redirection of wave energy downwards, followed by the zigzag dam, vertical seawall, riprap dam and curved seawall. The inverted dam is the most effective in reducing overtopping due to its narrow bottom lacking outward protrusion and redirection of wave energy downwards, followed by the zigzag dam, vertical seawall, riprap dam and curved seawall. The triangular dam, which was used as the control, was the least effective model due to the upward reflection of wave energy. To reduce overtopping in real life, a parapet can be attracted onto existing dams to redirect water downwards.

KEYWORDS: Coastal dam, Seawall, Erosion, Overtopping, Wave frequency

1. INTRODUCTION

Coastal erosion is an extremely significant problem which is exacerbated by flooding due to the overtopping of seawater over coastal dams. Climate change is a driving factor of rising sea levels, increasing coastal erosion and wave overtopping. For example, in Hemsby, Norfolk in England, coastal erosion has progressed to such an extent that residents had to be evacuated as houses were about to collapse into the sea¹. Furthermore, although it occurs over long periods of time, coastal erosion due to wave overtopping still results in extensive damage, especially to people or industries near the coast. Erosion causes about USD 500 million annually in coastal property losses, damages and loss of land.² Hence, coastal dams such as vertical seawalls, curved seawalls, and ripraps, are crucial in preventing wave overtopping and mitigating coastal flooding. These structures are designed to withstand the forces of waves and reduce the amount of water that overtops the structure, protecting inland areas from flooding and other damages, including soil erosion, which can lead to disasters like landslides.

Some common coastal dams include vertical seawalls, curved seawalls and riprap dams. Vertical seawalls are commonly employed in coastal defence due to their ability to withstand high-energy wave impacts. Research indicates that wave overtopping at vertical seawalls is influenced by several factors, including wave height, water level, and the slope of the foreshore. For instance, studies have shown that the evolution of the beach profile during storm sequences significantly affects overtopping volumes due to erosion. As the beach erodes, the water depth at the seawall increases, leading to greater overtopping during subsequent storms³. Curved seawalls are designed to redirect wave energy away from the structure and reduce overtopping. The curvature can help dissipate wave energy more effectively than vertical walls, potentially leading to lower overtopping rates. However, the effectiveness of curved seawalls can vary based on their design parameters and the incident wave conditions. Some studies suggest that while curved seawalls can reduce overtopping, they may not be as effective as anticipated under certain conditions, indicating a need for further research into their optimal design.³ Riprap dams, consisting of loose stones or boulders, serve as a flexible coastal defence mechanism. They are particularly effective in dissipating wave energy and reducing overtopping due to its rough surface and ability to absorb impact forces. The presence of riprap can significantly alter wave dynamics, leading to lower overtopping rates compared to vertical seawalls. Investigations have shown that the effectiveness of riprap is highly dependent on its size, placement, and the local wave climate⁴. However, the effectiveness of the curved seawall and riprap dams is highly dependent on factors like size and local wave climate, and may not be as effective as anticipated under certain circumstances.⁵

In a past paper⁶, the overtopping of coastal structures by tsunami waves was investigated. Using physical models, the overtopping of the dam-break structures affects the inundation height behind the structures was looked into. It was concluded that the energy of the approaching bore is a significant factor affecting overtopping, highlighting the importance of taking into account the velocity and inundation height of the wave at the beach. Dissipating wave energy at the beach by increasing roughness of the coastal structures was suggested. The height of water directly above and after the structure was for the low vertical wall was mostly lower than that of the dyke, possibly suggesting that the low vertical wall is better at reducing wave overtopping than the dyke. However, this may be attributed to the dyke being shorter than the low vertical wall. The low vertical wall is similar to vertical seawall, and the sloped shape of the dyke is similar to the triangular dam and riprap dam which we will be experimenting on.

A possible cause of overtopping is the constructive interference of coastal waves. When coastal waves hit the dam, the reflected wave may be in phase with the coastal waves, causing the waves to be amplified and overtop the dams. Different dam types possess various design qualities that result in diffusion, dissipation and redirection of incident waves, therefore causing reflected waves with the same amplitude in the opposite direction, contributing to destructive interference. Previous studies have not compared the influence of alternative geometries, such as zigzag or inverted triangle dams, on wave interference and overtopping performance. Thus, it is critical to understand how shapes affect the reflection and amplitude of the waves against the dam.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Model design and materials

To make the various dam models, compressed foam boards of dimensions 600x1200x50mm (EXT foam 600x1200x50mm blue), pebbles (DCR stone 500ml 7-15mm grey KNR PRND) and polystyrene glue (UHU por No:300) were used. Then, using an electric wire foam cutter (Hot wire foam cutter ST14402 by Woodland Scenics) and pen knives, 13 rectangular pieces of compressed foam of dimensions 28.5 x 26 x 5 cm were cut. For the vertical seawall and riprap dams, two rectangular pieces were glued together; for the curved, zigzag, and triangular dams, 3 rectangular pieces were glued together. Then, the blocks of foam were carved into shapes as shown in Figure 1(a). The

triangular dam was reused for the inverted triangle dam. Pebbles were glued to the surface of the riprap dam to create its rough texture, and pebbles were also glued onto the back of the other dam shapes to weigh the models down in the water, reducing floating.

2.2 Wave tank setup

Afterwards, the experiment was set up as shown in Figure 1(b). Ensure that the foam models are securely attached to the tank (58.5 x 28.5 x 33.5 cm) before filling the tank with 25L of water. The tank has a 18.8-75 rpm motor which moves the glass panel (28 x 0.5 x 30 cm). This glass panel, attached to the bottom of the tank, displaces and pushes the water in a back-and-forth motion to stimulate wave action. The generated waves are regular.

2.3 Measurement of data

Then, run the experiment using the lowest wave frequency of 0.313 Hz. Record a video of the side profile of the wave tank for 60 seconds. Repeat the experiment for the next 5 wave frequencies, 0.388, 0.650, 0.775, 1.16 and 1.25 Hz. These frequencies were chosen due to the limitations of the settings on the wave tank's motor. Repeat the experiment again using setups with the other 5 types of dams. Using the videos obtained, identify three points where the water was the highest and find the average distance between the water level at the start and the highest point the water reached as the maximum displacement of water.

Figure 1 (a) Cross section of the 6 different dam shapes being tested (not to scale). (b) Side view of experimental setup (not drawn to scale)

2.4 Safety

There is a risk of electric shock due to the electrical components not being waterproof. Should the electrical components come into contact with the water, it may cause the water to be electrified and electrocute people. To minimise this risk, unplug the tank when handling water and keep hands dry when turning on the tank. Hence, making sure that water does not come into contact with electrical components like the motor.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Table of average maximum vertical displacement of water for six wave frequencies for the six different dam models

Frequency of wave (Hz)	Vertical seawall (cm)	Curved seawall (cm)	Riprap (cm)	Zigzag (cm)	Inverted triangle (cm)	Triangular (cm)
0.313	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1
0.388	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
0.650	0.3	0.4	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.8
0.775	1.4	0.7	0.8	1.6	1.3	1.2
1.16	3.6	6.2	1.4	2.0	3.3	1.7
1.25	4.9	7.3	9.2	5.3	2.1	13.9

Figure 2 Graphs of the maximum vertical displacement of water to wave frequency with trend line. The curved seawall, riprap, zigzag and triangular dams follow an exponential trend, while the vertical seawall and inverted triangle dams follow a linear trend.

3.1 Key findings, comparison and explanations

The trend lines for the 6 different dam types as shown in Figure 2 indicate that the inverted triangle dam is the most effective in reducing overtopping, followed by the zigzag dam, vertical seawall, riprap dam, curved seawall and triangular dam.

The trend lines for the different dam types were chosen based on which trendline best fits the points, with the highest R^2 value. This allows us to understand more about the relationship of the frequency of wave and wave overtopping for different dam types.

From the data collected, vertical seawall and inverted triangle dams seem to be the most consistent as the relationship between the maximum vertical displacement of water and the frequency of the wave, which is related to the speed of the glass panel, is linear, with an R^2 value of 0.917 and 0.865 respectively, the linear trend matches the data points very closely, showing that the relationship is extremely linear. This may be due to the vertical seawall not reflecting as much wave impact as we have hypothesised, hence reducing the creation of in-phase waves that cause constructive interference.

Therefore, due to the little constructive interference produced, the wave amplitude stays approximately the same, creating a linear relationship between the speed of the glass panel and the maximum vertical displacement of water for vertical seawall. This may indicate that the vertical seawall and inverted triangle dams absorb wave impact more than they reflect wave impact. This suggests that absorbing wave impact is a crucial aspect of reducing wave overtopping.

Curved seawall dams and riprap dams have very similar results. The trend is exponential for both curved seawall and riprap dams, with an R^2 value of 0.984 and 0.679 respectively, showing that the trend fits an exponential trend line very well. The maximum vertical displacement of water stays quite low for both models until the wave frequency reaches 1.25 Hz, where the vertical displacement of water abruptly jumps to 7.3 cm and 9.2 cm for curved seawall and riprap dams respectively. The linear relationship shown in that of the vertical seawall suggests that this significant difference is likely not due to the tank or any other factors, and instead due to the odd shapes of these two dam types. The exponential behaviour observed in curved and riprap dams could be due to gradual energy dissipation by surface roughness, resulting in nonlinear energy dispersion. At the highest speed, the wave breaks following the curved shape of the seawall. Although the displacement of water is significantly high at this speed, the water is unable to reach a higher height because of the curved shape directing the flow of the water downwards and not upwards and above the dam. This indicates the effectiveness of the curved seawall dam in stopping overtopping of water. This suggests that geometry plays a crucial role in mitigating overtopping by decreasing wave height.

However, the inverted triangle dam has a significantly lower maximum vertical displacement of water than the curved seawall. When a wave parallel to the principal axis hits the inverted triangle dam, its angle of incidence causes a reflection of the wave downwards. Although both dam designs aim to reflect the wave energy downwards, the effectiveness of the inverted triangle dam suggests that the curved shape of the curved seawall is not ideal in reducing wave impact. This may be due to the bottom of the curved seawall directing the wave upwards, causing high maximum displacement of water, which is absent in the inverted triangle dam. Furthermore, both inverted triangle dams and curved seawall dams prevent the water from reaching a higher height above the dam due to the protruding parapet of the dam structure. Hence, this showcases the effectiveness of the inverted triangle dam over the curved seawall dam.

The zigzag dam has a significantly lower maximum vertical displacement than the riprap dam, suggesting that reflecting water downwards (the bottom portion of each triangular piece in the zigzag dam) is more effective than dispersing wave energy. Each triangular piece in the zigzag dam acts like an inverted triangle dam, pushing the water downwards and reducing overtopping. On the other hand, the ineffectiveness of the riprap dam may be due to the dam reflecting the wave upwards. The riprap dam model we use may not have enough rocks and the wave impact may not have been dissipated by the rocks enough. The remaining wave energy would have been reflected upwards by the general shape of the dam, significantly increasing the maximum vertical displacement of water. This may also indicate that there is a limit to the amount of energy the rocks can dissipate.

The triangular dam resulted in the highest maximum displacement of water, especially at the highest wave frequency of 1.25 Hz. This may be due to slope-induced shoaling, where the triangular shape of the dam causes the water to get shallower towards the top of the dam; wavelength decreases, and amplitude increases, resulting in the high vertical displacement of water. Another possible explanation of this would be that the triangular dam reflects the wave energy upwards, causing high vertical displacement of water and overtopping. When a wave parallel to the principal axis hits the triangular dam, its angle of incidence causes a reflection of the wave upwards. However, the R^2 value for the trendline of the triangular dam is not very high at 0.735. This is due to the maximum vertical displacement of water staying relatively low before abruptly spiking at the highest wave frequency. This may indicate that there may be a threshold for how much energy the dam can absorb, and if the wave frequency gets too high, more wave energy is reflected upwards instead, causing overtopping. This suggests that triangular dams are not effective for high frequencies but are effective in reducing

overtopping for lower frequencies, hence indicating that the angle of the slope of the dam is a key factor in wave steepening and directional reflection.

3.2 Evaluation of hypothesis

From the results obtained above, our hypothesis was proven wrong to some extent. The hypothesis that the triangular dam would be the least effective in reducing wave overtopping was proven right for high frequencies but incorrect for low frequencies. The hypothesis that the vertical seawall dam would not be effective in reducing the amount of wave overtopping was proven wrong and more effective than hypothesised. The hypothesis that zigzag dams would be more effective than riprap dams was proven correct, however, the hypothesis that curved seawall dams would be more effective than inverted triangle dams was proven incorrect. To summarise, inverted triangle dams are the most effective in reducing overtopping, followed by zigzag dams, vertical seawall, riprap dams, curved seawall dams and lastly, triangular dams.

Table 2 Visual ranking table to compare dam effectiveness based on different factors

Dam type	Absorption of wave impact	Energy dissipation	Decreasing wave height
Inverted triangle	✓		✓
Zigzag dam		✓	✓
Vertical seawall	✓		
Riprap dam		✓	
Curved seawall		✓	
Triangular			

3.3 Limitations and recommendations

The tank may not be an accurate representation of actual coastal areas as the wave gets reflected by a glass panel. In an actual coastal area, once the wave is reflected by the dam, it returns to the ocean after reflecting off the coast as there is typically no barrier blocking the wave from the ocean, like the glass panel in our setup. The glass panel in our setup causes wave interference that would not occur in an actual coastal setting. This discrepancy between the tank model and real life may cause inaccuracies in the data obtained. A way that this inaccuracy could be minimised is by using a longer tank. This way, after the wave is reflected by the dam model, it will lose energy travelling towards the other end of the dam and the interference the glass panel causes may be reduced. Another possible way this inaccuracy could be reduced is by using a rough surface on the other end of the tank to slightly diffuse the wave energy and minimise interference from the rebounded wave.

A combination of these two techniques can be a more effective method of reducing interference by the glass panel and ensuring that the simulation is more realistic. Furthermore, the material used to make the dam, compressed foam, is different from that used to make dams in real life, such as concrete and stone. The difference in the materials results in a difference in the hardness of the dams, resulting in the dam models being unable to recapitulate the ones in real life. For example, the foam being soft may absorb some of the wave impact instead of reflecting it, affecting the results of the experiment. The usage of foam was due to the unavailability of 3D-printers which could print such a large sized model and the impracticality of using a hard material like stone to carve the models out of. A way that this can be combated is to create the models out of foam and make a silicone mould out of it. Afterwards, fill in the mould with a hard material like concrete. Hence, the material used in the model and in real life would be the same and minimise any discrepancies between the two due to differences

in material used. Moreover, the dam models used could not represent aquatic life, such as shellfish like barnacles, that would be present on the surface of the dam in real life. These intricate organisms that make dam surfaces their habitat vary from place to place globally and would be difficult to recreate in a dam model. These structures may affect how the wave is reflected by the dam as the rough surface may absorb and diffuse wave impact. One possible way the texture of shellfish on the dam could be recreated is by analysing the surface of an existing shellfish-covered surface, such as by using a laser scanner or a silicone mould. Then, scale down the shellfish model to an appropriate size and stick 3D models of each individual shellfish onto the surface of the dam model which is underwater, hence allowing the dam models to be more realistic. These biofouling organisms increase surface roughness, which can enhance energy dissipation by reducing reflective wave energy and promoting turbulence near the structure's surface. It must also be noted that such qualities of a dam also differ globally, and one model is not representative of the features of all coastal dams.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, inverted triangle dams, zigzag dams and vertical seawall dams are effective in reducing overtopping, with inverted triangle dams being the most effective. This suggests that reflecting wave energy downwards is effective, with the use of an overarching parapet being useful in blocking water from overtopping. Furthermore, as the triangular dam was designed to mimic coastal regions, and is the least effective in reducing overtopping, it highlights the importance of coastal dams in protecting coastal areas from flooding and erosion. Unexpectedly, the curved seawall and riprap dams, which are commonly used, are not very effective in reducing overtopping, indicating that these dams have certain limitations.

Through this research, we have contributed information on the relationship between the different dam shapes, such as flat or curved shapes and textures like smooth or rocky, in mitigating wave overtopping. These findings help contribute to the development of better dam designs that can withstand the more volatile coastal conditions climate change brings about and reduce flooding and coastal erosion. Therefore, this knowledge also contributes to UN Sustainable Development Goal 13: Climate Action, by providing insights into effective coastal defence strategies, allowing us to mitigate climate change's impacts and build resilience to flooding and coastal erosion.

This research demonstrated the effectiveness of inverted triangle dams in reducing overtopping. An upwards sloping parapet can be attached onto existing dams to redirect the water downwards, increasing the effectiveness of the dams as shown in Figure 3. However, shapes like the inverted triangle dam and zigzag dam may not be durable in the long-term. Instead, vertical seawalls may be used as it is able to withstand large wave forces. Such dams can be applied to flood-prone areas, such as low-lying communities living near coastal areas or those prone to coastal erosion with loose soil, to help improve public safety and reduce financial losses due to property destruction.

Figure 3 Diagram of a modified dam design combining the inverted triangular dam (the protruding portion at the top) with a vertical seawall.

Further investigation into various dam types can be done, including different designs of riprap dams and our own design ideas. Riprap dams can consist of rocks or other concrete structures of different shapes, each having unique characteristics and effectiveness in diffusing wave impact. Furthermore, the gaps between these structures can allow for aquatic life, such as shellfish, to thrive in the safety of the dam. Additionally, more research can be conducted to understand semi-permeable dams in maintaining the aquatic ecosystem while also protecting the coastal areas from erosion. Lastly, further study into how the different wave frequencies can impact the wave overtopping of the various dam types is needed. Our current research shows that there is a significant difference between high-frequency and low-frequency waves in the maximum vertical displacement of water, more research should be done in this area to understand more about the relationship between frequency of waves and overtopping.

This research highlights the critical role of dam engineering and geometry in controlling wave overtopping and offers a novel direction for designing resilient coastal infrastructure in the face of challenges posed by rising sea levels due to global warming.

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L.H.Y. and A.E. conducted the experiment, contributed to the conception, data analysis and drafting of the manuscript.

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